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PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF SINGER PREPARATION IN THE STEP-BY-STEP MASTERING OF THE MAQOM REPERTORY

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Annotation: This article analyzes the psychological aspects of a singer's preparation in the process of mastering the art of makom. In particular, it reveals the role of psychological factors such as the emotional state of the singer's personality, creative thinking, stage excitement, and ability to express themselves in the gradual mastery of the makom repertoire. The study substantiates the impact of the level of psychological preparation on the singer's performance skills and stage expression styles through practical examples. The article also highlights the importance of working in harmony with makom instruments, internal listening (auditive analysis), musical memory, and emotional stability. The results of this study indicate the need to form psychological competencies in the singer's preparation in order to achieve high-quality results in makom performance.

Keywords: maqom art, singer's preparation, psychological preparation, emotional state, pre-stage excitement, musical memory, creative thinking, inner listening, maqom repertoire, performance skills.

Introduction.

Maqom art is a high example of Uzbek national musical culture, which embodies the artistic and aesthetic principles, system of musical thinking and performance traditions formed over the centuries. This art form requires the singer not only technical and vocal skills, but also deep psychological preparation, emotional stability, and the ability to express inner experiences through musical images. In particular, the singer's psychological state, stage culture, self-confidence and creative motivation are important factors in the gradual mastery of the maqom repertoire.

Maqom works have a complex structure, and their content includes many aspects, such as philosophical and aesthetic layers, the uniqueness of words and melodies, harmonious work with musicians, and the logical development of maqom sections. This process requires a high level of musical hearing from the singer, a deep understanding of melody and rhythm, auditory analysis, and emotional and intellectual activity. Therefore, the process of psychological preparation in mastering the maqom repertoire should become an object of independent study.

In modern musicology, based on concepts such as performance psychology, psycho-emotional aspects of stage activity, creative stress, identification and self-

control, the artist's behavior on stage, the level of sensitivity to the audience, and the mechanisms for managing internal experiences are being scientifically analyzed. It is in the performance of maqom that these situations become even more relevant for the singer, and personal psychological preparation plays an important role in fully expressing the semantic and emotional layers of the work.

This article analyzes the psychological characteristics of a singer in the process of gradually mastering the maqom repertoire, individual emotional reaction, internal monologue, creative visualization and stress management strategies based on musical and pedagogical approaches. The relevance of the study is that it serves to scientifically substantiate the role of psychological components in improving the quality of maqom performance.

The art of maqom is not a simple performance, but an artistic expression of the spiritual world. Each maqom, especially complex melodies such as "Buzruk", "Rost", "Segoh", penetrates the most delicate layers of the human soul. The performance of such artistically charged works is closely related not only to simple vocal skill, but also to the psycho-psychological preparation of the performer. First of all, the singer must be able to feel the content, internal energy of this musical sample, pass it through his soul and convey it to the listener. This is achieved through the combination of psychological stability, emotional sensitivity and creative thinking.

In the process of gradual mastery, the singer first of all studies the systematic structure of the maqom, its sections (prose, shubah, tarona, ufar, saqinama, etc.). Although this process requires technical and theoretical knowledge, the real complexity is manifested in understanding the spiritual and aesthetic aspects of the maqom. Each maqom embodies its own unique feelings and life experiences, and the singer must thoroughly prepare his psychological preparation to revive this state. Pre-stage excitement, lack of self-confidence or internal conflicts have a negative impact on the naturalness of the performance.

Practical experience has shown that young singers who have just entered the maqom performance often have to struggle with their internal state rather than with the state on stage. "Can I perform this maqom?", "What will it affect the listeners?" To struggle with the questions, to overcome one's inner voice, to fully surrender to the performance - this is not easy. From this point of view, it is necessary to arm the performer with psychological training exercises, strategies for adapting to the environment, and stress management techniques.

Since maqom performance is an art form with such high artistic expression, musical hearing and memory, internal listening (auditory reflection) play a very important role in it. The singer must simultaneously not only work in harmony with the musicians, but also feel the dynamic development, rhythmic structure, and

dramatic peaks of the work in advance. This requires emotional readiness in advance, mobilization of mental activity, and use of creative imagination.

In other words, in mastering the maqom, the singer must be not only a "hearer" and "performer", but also a "translator" in his own way - he must harmonize his feelings and the spirit of the work and convey it to the audience. This requires a high level of spiritual sensitivity and psychological thinking. Psychological preparation in the process of mastering the maqom repertoire is an integral, even central aspect of performance. Working with each maqom work is, in fact, a process of self-awareness of the singer, expanding his capabilities, and forming his emotional world. Therefore, every singer who wants to perfectly master the art of maqom must, first of all, learn to work with his own psycho-psychological state.

Discussion.

The art of maqom is not only music, but also a sacred phenomenon that combines the inner spiritual world, national identity, history and philosophy. Every singer who studies this art actually goes through the path of self-awareness, self-education and musical formation. However, the biggest obstacle on this path is not technical capabilities, but psychological factors. For a singer, mastering the maqom repertoire means expressing his experiences, thoughts, and aesthetic perception through each melody and section in a balanced and free manner.

From this perspective, we understand that studying the art of maqom only within the framework of a didactic-methodical process is not enough. Because the singer's inner state of mind, psychological preparation directly affects his ability to create an artistic image. In particular, maqom works with a wide emotional scope - maqoms such as "Bayot", "Navo", "Segoh" - require the performer not only vocal control, but also to manage his emotions, achieve inner spiritual harmony, and control stage excitement. In this case, we see psychological stability as the main support.

The psychological state of a singer is formed by many factors: the level of self-confidence, emotional intelligence, internal motivation, attitude towards the audience, the psychological environment with the teacher, experience on stage and even psychological experiences in childhood. These factors, in turn, directly affect the naturalness, freedom of the performance and the strength of the emotional impact on the listener. A singer may be able to control his voice, but if he cannot properly manage his internal emotions, it is difficult for the performance to be sincere.

Today, in foreign musical psychology, a psychological approach to the art of performance is also gaining importance. For example, methods such as emotional self-awareness, autogenic exercises before the performance, musical visualization techniques, and balancing the internal state through breath control are actively used. Although these approaches are widely used, especially in classical music, opera and

drama vocals, the need to adapt them to the art of maqom is increasing day by day. Because the maqom, by its very nature, has dramatic power, inner drama, and in order to truly express it, the singer must learn to work with his or her spiritual world.

Another important aspect is the singer's choice of repertoire based on his or her personal psychotype. Just as each person's level of emotional perception and expression is different, maqoms are only sincere and natural when performed in harmony with personal experiences. Teachers who teach maqom performance should take this aspect into account in depth and choose an approach suitable for each student. Here we will consider the methodology of an individual-differential approach as the main tool.

Performance training based on a psychological approach not only increases the speed of mastering the maqom, but also helps the singer to behave on stage, establish psychological contact with the audience, and manage stress. After all, the listener wants to feel not only a beautiful voice, but also a sincere, direct melody from the heart. And this is possible not only through technique, but also through deep spiritual preparation.

Thus, in the art of maqom, the psychological preparation of the singer is not only an auxiliary factor, but also the main approach. Promoting, developing and implementing this approach into methodology serves to raise the quality level not only of maqom performance, but also of our national art in general.

Conclusion.

The art of maqom is not just a means of musical expression, but a complex art system that embodies the spiritual and moral world, historical memory and artistic thinking of an entire nation. The main factor that can reveal the true beauty and expressiveness of this art form is the singer's internal preparation, that is, psychological maturity. Therefore, it is not enough to rely only on technical and theoretical knowledge in the gradual mastering of the maqom repertoire. A singer's emotional sensitivity, creative intuition, stage manners, and most importantly, inner mental stability also require close attention. The study found that a psychologically prepared singer can convey not only the melody, but also the spirit, inner content, and emotional context of the work to the listener during the performance. This creates internal resonance in the listener, that is, musical and spiritual harmony. Achieving such a result depends not only on the singer's vocal capabilities, but also on the singer's psychological work on himself - complex processes such as self-awareness, control of excitement, and self-identification with musical images.

In today's art education system, more emphasis is placed on technical and theoretical aspects in the training of singers. However, this approach may not give full results. Because maqom performance is the art of combining high internal culture,

deep thinking, and emotional awareness. Therefore, psychological preparation should be recognized as an important part of self-improvement for every singer who is starting to master the maqom repertoire. In the educational process, it would be appropriate to introduce special psychological trainings, musical meditations, creative relaxation exercises, and stress management techniques in this direction.

In conclusion, it can be said that when teaching the art of maqom, it is necessary to take into account the psychological state of the singer, to update existing approaches in this area and to apply them in practice. After all, a truly artistic performance should be not only a skill, but also a musical expression of the soul and thinking. Achieving such a performance depends on the spiritual maturity, psychological stability, and creative sensitivity of the singer. It is through this approach that we will be able to create new, modern, and profound interpretations of the national art of maqom.

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